

Effect of Supply Chain Risk Management Strategies on Performance of Fast Food Chains in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The fast food industry has played a significant role in expanding economic opportunities, affecting human life and health, while also strongly influencing the entire value chain from growers to consumers. With the overarching goal of examining the effect of supply chain risk management strategies on the performance of fast food firms in the South-South region of Nigeria, the target population for the study comprised all fast food firms in the region. From the research population of 499 fast food firms in the South-South, Nigeria, and 10,064 employees, Taro Yamane was used to determine a sample size of 385 staff in five departments in each of the firms sampled. A four-point Likert scale questionnaire was administered to senior-level managers with knowledge of supply-chain and logistics functions, using both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data obtained. Findings showed that supply chain risk management strategies have a significant influence on the performance of fast food firms. Also, the most important SCRM strategies on the performance of a fast food firm were the SC avoidance strategies, while the second most influential SCRM strategies on the performance of a fast food firm were the SC control strategies. It concludes that Supply base rationalization strategies have the least influence on fast food firms. The study recommends, among others, that fast food firms should adopt risk control strategies that allow collaboration with their supply chain members for their business as a matter of necessity, as this will help to protect them against risk.

Keywords: *Supply Chain Resilience, Risk Management Strategies, Risk Avoidance, Risk Control Strategies, Performance.*

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Introduction

Supply chains have become more susceptible to unpredictable events that could lead to supply

disruptions and undermine supply chain performance (Kihyun, 2012). Globally, no other industry is more dependent on public confidence than the food and beverage industry

(including the fast food sectors), which in contemporary times exhibits more vulnerability to disruptive risks (Roth, Tsay, Pullman & Gray, 2008). According to Sheffi (2005), without appropriate strategies in place to deal with these risks, companies could become vulnerable to disruptions. In the literature, supply chain risks are shown to influence supply chain performance. Kern et al. (2012) focused on the process dimensions of upstream SCRM and showed that competent SCRM in companies leads to superior performance. Papadakis (2006) investigated the vulnerability of supply chains empirically by analyzing and comparing the stock performance of firms facing supply disruptions. The study indicated that a supply chain with a high level of risk couldn't be efficient. Schmitt (2011) analytically models supply disruptions in a multi-echelon supply chain and numerically demonstrates the effectiveness of supply chain risk management strategies. Hendricks and Singhal (2005), in an empirical study, reported that supply chain disruptions could lead to a company's long-term negative financial performance, especially in terms of shareholder wealth and stock returns when compared to an industry benchmark.

The phenomenon of globalisation and the practice of outsourcing have prompted several industrial organisations to opt for supply chain and logistics management as a means to effectively oversee their operations (Van Der Vors & Beulens, 2002). Supply chain disruptions cause a sales fall of 7%, a drop in operating income of 42%, and a fall in return on assets of 35%, and an announcement of supply chain disruptions causes a shareholder return between 7 and 8% (Hendricks & Singhal, 2005). In the context of Nigeria, and most especially the fast food chains in the South-South region of the country, the challenges are diverse: short shelf life and perishability, stiff competition from traditional food restaurants, and increased consumer safety and health concerns (IGNOU, 2017; Bianchi & Venturi, 2025). The short shelf life and perishability of food and beverage products, along with the challenges of infrastructure, pose a serious threat to fast food firms. Secondly, consumer concerns about environmental and welfare issues have raised

expectations of fast food managers to ensure food products are produced sensitively and safely (Hamad, 2012 ; Licoli & Calligaris, 2018; Lohita & Sriyaya, 2024).

Innovation and technological advancements are crucial for these businesses to meet consumer demands and preferences, as well as adapt to the rapidly evolving food landscape. It is important to note that fast food consumption in Nigeria is subject to cultural and societal influences, with many Nigerians favoring traditional foods and dining experiences over Western-style fast food. Therefore, understanding the local context and tailoring strategies accordingly is essential for success in the Nigerian fast food market.

According to Samir & Aman (2010), management of food and beverage supply chains requires speed, accuracy, and intelligent decision-making to cope with the complex, dynamic competition and uncertainty from external demands and variables. In order to attain that, several strategies exist towards supply chain risk management (Tang & Musa, 2011). Effective supply chain risk management strategies are integral to the growth and survival of any business venture (Desroches, Hatch, & Lawson, 2014; Ruetschlin, 2014). Adopting effective business strategies in the fast food industry is paramount to the growth and survivability of fast food businesses (Mann, Adebajo, & Kehoe, 1998; Min & Min, 2013). The low-profit margins in the fast food industry were reported to have stemmed from the failure of fast food restaurant managers to follow their effective business strategies (Min & Min, 2013). Fast food businesses may succeed if their managers follow effective business strategies in running their restaurants.

The lack of effective supply chain risk management strategies may contribute to the failure of fast food restaurants in Nigeria (Adisa, Abdulraheem, & Mordi, 2014; Osakwe, 2016). Approximately 80% of fast food restaurants launched in Nigeria in 2014 failed to survive beyond 5 years (Sahagun & Vasquez-Parraga, 2014). The general business problem is that managers embark on small business initiatives without adequate preparation. The specific business problem is that some fast food business

managers lack the appropriate resilient capabilities to manage properly the supply chain risks associated with their businesses. A number of studies have focused on supply chain risk management in different industries, such as the retail industry (Oke & Gopalakrishnan, 2009), toy industry (Johnson, 2001), personal computer industry (Papadakis, 2006), consumer electronics industry (Sodhi & Lee, 2007), and aerospace supply chain (Sinha, Whitman & Malzahn, 2004).

While there has been a significant amount of research conducted in the area of supply chain resilience, there has been relatively little reported about the influence of supply chain risk management strategies on the performance of fast food firms, hence the need for this study. More specifically, this study measured the performance of fast food chains against the supply chain risk management strategies using three evaluation objects/variables (supply base rationalisation strategies, supply chain risk control strategies, and supply chain risk avoidance strategies).

Conceptual, Theoretical, and Empirical Foundations

Supply Chain Risk Avoidance Strategies

Risk avoidance is the most effective risk management strategy in that by avoiding an activity, any chance of loss is eliminated (Khan & Burnes, 2007; Tuncel & Alpan, 2010). Avoidance strategies are classified as Type 1 and Type 2 (Manuj & Mentzer, 2008). Type 1 avoidance strategy is used when the risks associated with operating in a given product or geographical market, or working with particular suppliers or customers, are considered unacceptable. Manuj and Mentzer (2008) suggested that avoidance takes the form of exiting through divestment of specialized assets, delay of entry into a market or market segment, or participating only in low uncertainty markets. This type of strategy is geared toward driving overall probabilities associated with risk events of a decision to zero by ensuring that the risk does not exist (Tang & Tomlin, 2008; Manuj & Mentzer, 2008). In avoiding risks, managers are aware of the supply-demand and/or operating

trade-offs associated with the options and choose to avoid or drop some of these risks (Ghadge *et al.*, 2013). Avoidance strategy Type 2 takes the form of preempting adverse events (Manuj & Mentzer, 2008).

Supply Chain Control Strategies

Supply chain risk control is the process of taking proactive steps to reduce the identified risks where possible and putting procedures, rules, or policies in place to minimize the residual risk or to reduce the severity of such a loss (Hepenstal & Boon, 2007; Son & Orchard, 2012). Effective supply chain risk management requires supporting infrastructure, which is executive-led (Flynn, Huo & Zao, 2010; Lockamy, 2014). It has been viewed that companies have been implementing different strategies and philosophies to control inventory, to eliminate waste, bring continuous improvement, to improve forecasting, and improve efficiency and responsiveness (Christopher, Peck & Towill 2006; Kleindorfer & Saad, 2005).

SC Network Theory

According to Chopra *et al.* (2007) a supply contract specifies what governs the buyer-supplier relationship as it guides the behavior and performance of all the parties. In addition to volume or capacity, lead time, price, and liabilities, penalties are part of the contracts. Contracts are structured to increase profitability, reduce risks by giving accurate information, and enhance flexibility. Dekker, Sakaguchi, and Kawai (2013) also stated that well-specified contracts might actually promote more cooperative, long-term, trusting exchange relationships. Well-specified contracts narrow the domain and severity of risk to which an exchange is exposed, and thereby encourage cooperation and trust. Dekker *et al.* (2004) also argue that contracts and relationships are complementary. Using structured contractual mechanisms, organizations can improve and coordinate better with suppliers and secure different supply options (Chopra *et al.*, 2007). Micheli *et al.* (2008) have said that suppliers are vital to the success of a firm, in terms of their reliability in availability and on the competitive edge of the final product, impact the level of risk. Supplier selection, diversification, supplier

partnership and interaction, contract agreement, are some of the strategies used to manage supply chain risks. Hence, the study hypothesized the relationship between supply base strategies and performance in fast food firms.

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

The study area is the South-south region of Nigeria, located between latitudes 5° 00'N and 6° 30'N and longitudes 5° 20'E and 9° 00'E (see Figure 1). The region comprises six States, which are: Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers. The South-south region, with the Niger River, is situated directly on the Gulf of Guinea on the Atlantic Ocean in Nigeria.

Figure 1. The South-South States and their Capital Cities

Source: Open Street Mapping, 2022

Materials and Methods

The study adopted a selection criterion of the target populations to include managers, procurement or purchasing officers, logistics officers, warehousing or store officers, and supervisors of fast food chains in South-South Nigeria with annual sales between 5,000,000 and 20,000,000 Naira, as well as a minimum number of 10 employees that have been in business longer than 5 years. Specifically, the sampled population of fast food firms in the South-South

region of Nigeria was four hundred and ninety-nine (499) firms with ten thousand and sixty-four (10,064) employees. Taro Yamane was used to determine the sample size of 385. The purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants for this study because it allowed the researcher to engage participants with relevant experience and knowledge about the fast food business. A questionnaire instrument was used to collect data from the participants, while descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used for the analysis. The data were presented using frequency and percentage tables, while the hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation statistics.

Results and Discussion

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 presents the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. Item #1 indicates the gender distribution of the respondents and shows that 54.8% were female, while 45.2% were male. Item #2 shows the age distribution of the respondents and reveals that 31.86% of respondents were within the ages of 28 - 37 years and 38 - 47 years, while 25.48% and 10.8% of respondents were within 18 – 27 years and 48 years and above, respectively. In addition, item #3 revealed that 55.96% of the respondents were married, while 32.1% were single. Item #4 revealed the educational attainment of the respondents, which further revealed that 77.6% and 22.4% of respondents had a tertiary education and secondary education, respectively. The sixth item (i.e., item #6) on the tables indicates the position and department of the respondents, from which 19.7% of respondents were joint managers, as well as procurement officers, 19.4% were logistics officers, 18.3% were in the warehousing and store department, and 23% were supervisors.

Table 1. Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 361)

S/N	Variables	Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Male	163	45.2%
		Female	198	54.8%
2	Age Range	18 – 27 Years	92	25.48%
		28 – 37 Years	115	31.86%
		38 – 47 Years	115	31.86%
		48 Years & Above	39	10.80%
3	Marital Status	Single	116	32.1%
		Married	202	55.96%
		Separated	17	4.7%
		Divorced	26	7.2%
4	Educational Qualification	Secondary	81	22.4%
		Tertiary	280	77.6%
5	Average Monthly Income	Less than N30,000	38	10.5%
		N30,000 – N70,000	165	45.7%
		N71,000 – N100,000	106	29.4%
		N101,000 & Above	52	14.4%
6	Position/Department in the Organization	Manager	71	19.7%
		Procurement/Purchasing	71	19.7%
		Logistics Officer	70	19.4%
		Warehousing/Store	66	18.3%
		Supervisor	83	23.0%
7	Years of Experience in the Current Firm	1 – 5 Years	150	41.6%
		6 – 10 Years	173	47.9%
		11 – 15 Years	38	10.5%
8	Number of Employees	10 – 49	361	100%
9	Age/Length of Time in Existence	6 – 10 Years	209	57.9%
		11 – 15 Years	139	38.5%
		16 – 20 Years	13	3.6%

Source: Researcher’s Analysis, 2025

Furthermore, the number of employees of the firms in the study area as presented in Table 1 as item #8, show that all the firms 100% of total respondents had 10 - 49 employees. Finally, the age and length of time the fast food firms have been in existence (item #9) reveals that majority (57.9%) of the fast food outlets had been in existence between 6 – 10 years, 38.5% of the total respondents said their fast food outlets had been in existence between 11 – 15 years, while 3.6% said their fast food outlets had been in existence between 16 – 20 years. The implication is that all the fast food firms 100% that participated in the study have been in business longer than 5 years, which is one of the criteria for participation.

Influence of Supply Chain Risk Control Strategies on Performance

From Table 2, item Q#CS1 shows that respondents who agreed that their fast food outlets do use holding of underutilized capacity, which serves as a cushion to any disruptions as a supply chain risk control strategy, had the highest response of 78.9%, while those who disagreed had the lowest response of 6.9%. The high mean score of 3.72 indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed. Since the mean score of 3.72 is ≥ 2.5 , we thereby accept the statement that fast food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria do use holding of underutilized capacity, which serves as a cushion to any disruptions as a supply chain risk control strategy. In addition, item Q#CS4 shows that respondents who agreed that their fast food outlets do use centralised decision making as a

supply chain risk control strategy had the highest response of 78.9%, while those who disagreed had the lowest response of 8.6%. Also, the high mean score of 3.04 is ≥ 2.5 ; we thereby accept

the statement that fast food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria do use centralised decision-making as a supply chain risk control strategy.

Table 2. Influence of Supply Chain Risk Control Strategies on Performance

S/N	Items	Strongly Disagree Freq (%)	Disagree Freq (%)	Agree Freq (%)	Strongly Agree Freq (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
CS1	Holding of underutilized capacity which serves as a cushion to any disruptions		25 (6.9%)	51 (14.1%)	285 (78.9%)	3.7191	.58620
CS2	Holding of buffer stock to mitigate the risk of stock-out	38 (10.5%)	256 (70.9%)	16 (4.4%)	51 (14.1%)	2.2274	.82033
CS3	Regular monitoring of supply chain risks (demand, supply, process and environmental risks).			270 (74.8%)	91 (25.2%)	3.2508	.43422
CS4	Centralised decision making		31 (8.6%)	285 (78.9%)	45 (12.5%)	3.0368	.45831
CS5	Our products are highly competitive in the industry		18 (5.0%)	256 (70.9%)	87 (24.1%)	3.1906	.50545
CS6	Competitive advantage is greatly experienced			88 (24.4%)	273 (75.6%)	3.7559	.43030
CS7	Products /goods are delivered in the right quality and quantities	170 (47.1%)	60 (16.6%)	63 (17.5%)	68 (18.8%)	2.0769	1.18042

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

Also in item Q#CS5, respondents who agreed that their fast food products are highly competitive in the industry had the highest response of 70.9%, while those who disagreed had the lowest response of 5.0%. Also, the high mean score of 3.19 indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed. Item Q#CO6 shows that respondents who agreed that competitive advantage is greatly experienced by their fast food firms had the highest response of 75.6%, while the remaining respondents agreed with the response of 24.4%. Also, the high mean score of 3.78 indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed. Since the mean score of 3.78 is ≥ 2.5 , we thereby accept the statement that competitive advantage is greatly experienced by the fast food chains in South-South, Nigeria.

Effect of Supply Chain Risk Avoidance Strategies on Performance

From Table 3, item Q#A1 shows that respondents who strongly agreed that their fast food firms avoid some suppliers in order to minimize supply chain risks had the highest response of 64%, while those who agreed had the lowest response of 36%. The high mean score of 3.64 indicates that all the respondents agreed. Since the mean score of 3.64 is ≥ 2.5 , we thus accept the statement that fast food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria avoid some suppliers in order to minimize supply chain risks. In addition, item Q#A2 shows that respondents who agreed that their fast food firms delay getting into certain markets until the uncertainty is reduced had the highest response of 72.6%, while those who disagreed had the lowest response of 1.1%. Also, the high mean score of

3.25 further indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed.

Also in item Q#A4, respondents who strongly agreed that their fast food firms used information technology to reduce supply chain risks had the highest response of 64%, while the remaining respondents, with a response of 36%, agreed. The high mean score of 3.64 further indicates that all the respondents agreed that in their fast food firms, information technology is used to reduce supply chain risks. Item Q#A7

shows that respondents who strongly agreed that in their fast food chains, there is minimal cost of customer maintenance had the highest response of 42.7%, while those who strongly disagreed had the lowest response of 6.4%. Also, the relatively high mean score of 2.98 indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed. Since the mean score of 2.98 is ≥ 2.5 , we thereby accept the statement that there is minimal cost of customer maintenance in the fast food chains in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 3. Effect of Supply Chain Risk Avoidance Strategies on Performance

S/N	Items	Strongly Disagree Freq (%)	Disagree Freq (%)	Agree Freq (%)	Strongly Agree Freq (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
A1	Our firm avoids some suppliers in order to minimize supply chain risks			130 (36.0%)	231 (64.0%)	3.6388	.48115
A2	Our firm delays getting into certain markets until the uncertainty is reduced		4 (1.1%)	262 (72.6%)	95 (26.3%)	3.2542	.45863
A3	Our firm audits both our processes and supplier processes to minimize quality risks			288 (79.8%)	73 (20.2%)	3.2007	.40117
A4	Our firm information technology is used to reduce supply chain risks			130 (36.0%)	231 (64.0%)	3.6388	.48115
A5	There is reduction of waste in terms of usage and storage	24 (6.6%)	269 (74.5%)	52 (14.4%)	16 (4.4%)	2.1639	.59913
A6	The degree of customer satisfaction have greatly improved	17 (4.7%)	139 (38.5%)	109 (30.2%)	96 (26.6%)	2.7893	.89316
A7	Minimal cost of customer maintenance	23 (6.4%)	115 (31.8%)	69 (19.1%)	154 (42.7%)	2.9833	1.00154

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

HO1: Supply chain risk control strategies have no positive influence on the performance of fast

food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria.

Table 4. Correlations Result for Hypothesis One**

		Control Strategies	Performance
Spearman's rho	Control Strategies	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	361
	Performance	Correlation Coefficient	.380**
			1.000

		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	361	361

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2025

From the results table 4, the correlation coefficient (rho) showed that supply chain risk control strategies have a significant effect on the performance of fast food chains in South-South, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient of 0.380 confirms the extent and strength of this influence, and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, based on empirical findings, the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternative upheld. Thus, the supply chain risk control strategies have a positive and significant effect on the performance of fast food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria. The research findings are in agreement with Lockamy (2014), who revealed that

companies have been implementing different strategies and philosophies to control inventory, to eliminate waste, bring continuous improvement, improve forecasting, and improve efficiency and responsiveness. The finding is also in consonance with the previous findings (Wang, 2018; Raju & Lonial, 2001), who concluded that Supply chain uncertainty and risk have a significant impact on organizational performance.

Hypothesis Two

HO2: Supply chain risk avoidance strategies have no positive influence on the performance of fast food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria.

Table 5. Correlation Results for Hypothesis Three

			Avoidance Strategies	Perform Ance
Spearman's rho	Avoidance Strategies	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.716**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	361	361
	Performance	Correlation Coefficient	.716**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	361	361

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2025

The correlation coefficient (rho) result in Table 5 shows that supply chain risk avoidance strategies have a significant effect on the performance of fast food chains in South-South, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient of 0.716 confirms the extent and strength of this influence, and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, based on empirical findings, the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternative upheld. Thus, the supply chain risk avoidance strategies have a positive and significant effect on the performance of fast food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria. The study findings tally with those of

Christopher & Holweg (2011), who found that supply chains operating in all types of environments attempt to avoid risks within the constraints of acceptable returns, such as revenue and profit targets. Hence, avoidance strategies lead to better SC performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, in a changing and challenging environment, fast food businesses must advance their supply chains beyond the traditional. Without a strategic focus on supply-chain risk management, supply chain operations can rapidly deteriorate, putting quality, profitability,

and lives in danger. From a managerial standpoint, it becomes important to understand and actively manage all the supply chain disruptions that influence business performance and continuity of organizations. Firms need to realize that the importance of their supply chain resilience capabilities is crucial during supply chain disruptions. The implementation of supply chain risk management strategies, such as risk avoidance, risk control, and supply base rationalisation strategies, is necessary to ensure the continuity of businesses. From the findings of the correlation analysis, this study concludes that the most important Supply Chain Risk Management strategies for the performance of a fast food firm are the supply chain risk avoidance strategies. Based on the above empirical findings, it can be concluded that Supply chain risk management strategies have a significant influence on the performance of fast food chains in the South-South region of Nigeria.

The study thereby recommends that fast food firms should adopt risk control strategies that allow collaboration with their supply chain members for their business as a matter of necessity, as this could help to protect them against risk. Avoidance strategies, such as delaying entry to uncertain markets and total avoidance of such markets, are vital to fast food firms' supply chain competence. Additionally, firms cannot escape supply chain risks, but combining the right capabilities with an effective avoidance strategy may lead to a successful supply chain.

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